

INFLUENCE OF FOREIGN CONTEMPORARY MUSIC ON UZBEKI NATIONAL PUBLIC ART

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Abstract: This article analyzes the impact of foreign modern music on the Uzbek national pop music. As a result of globalization and technological development, the significant influence of Western music genres and styles on national pop music is studied. The integration of genres such as pop, hip-hop, rap, electronica, dance, rock, R&B and fusion into Uzbek pop music is shown through examples. As a result of these influences, Uzbek national music has modern tones and forms of expression, has become popular among young people and has created an opportunity to be known internationally. The article describes how Uzbek artists have adapted to these processes and their success in creating new musical trends. As a result, it is emphasized that foreign modern music has made a great contribution to the development and modernization of Uzbek pop music.

Keywords: Contemporary pop, national pop, Western music, Pop, hip-hop, rap, electronica, disco, dance, rock, R&B, reggae, fusion, global influence.

Introduction:

Foreign music has had a significant impact on Uzbek pop music. Historically, this effect is divided into several stages:

1. Influence of the Soviet era.

During the Soviet period, the musical environment of Uzbekistan underwent extensive cultural changes. Classical and folk music typical of the countries of the Soviet Union also influenced Uzbekistan. During this period, many Uzbek musicians were educated throughout the Soviet Union, and this was reflected in their music.

2. Influence of Western music

In the 1980s and 1990s, especially after Uzbekistan gained independence, Western music entered Uzbek pop music. Pop, rock, and other modern genres became popular. During this period, many Uzbek artists began to use elements of Western music in their works, and through this, artists combined Western melodies and styles with Uzbek folk music in their music.

3. Modern global influence

Today, due to globalization, music from different parts of the world has a great influence on the musical culture of Uzbekistan. Through the Internet and social networks, Uzbek artists follow world music and try different genres and styles in their works. This serves to enrich the new Uzbek pop music and make it competitive at the international level.

The influence of foreign modern music on the Uzbek national pop music has been significantly reflected in various aspects. These influences contributed to the modernization of Uzbek national music and its international recognition.

Western music introduced many new genres and styles to Uzbek pop music. Pop, hip-hop, electronica, R&B, disco, rock and many other genres were adopted by Uzbek artists and performed in their own way. This process helped create new forms of national music. Production and mixing technologies play a big role in modern music. The experience gained from Western music is also widely used in Uzbek pop music. Music tracks created with the help of computer programs and high-tech studios are increasingly used by Uzbek artists. This helps to improve the quality of music and to meet international standards. Contemporary Western music has also had a great influence on stage appearance and performance style. The new generation of Uzbek artists are introducing dance, show elements and fashion innovations in their performances. This serves to attract the audience more and make the musical performances more attractive.

Cooperation with foreign artists played an important role in the development of Uzbek pop music. A number of Uzbek artists participated in international projects, expanded their musical knowledge and conquered new audiences. These collaborations brought Uzbek music to the international arena. The influence of Western music is also visible in the lyrical themes. In Uzbek pop music, love, friendship, social issues, and even global issues are now expressed in more songs. This gives modern spirit to national music and makes it popular among young people.

Uzbek pop music is closely connected with international musical trends, and these connections are expected to continue in the future. Western pop music had a great influence on Uzbek pop music. Pop music with its light and cheerful tones has spread widely among Uzbek musicians. Bojalar group, Shahzoda, Shokhrukhan, Jo'rabek, Sagdiyana, Lola, Rayhon, Yulduz Usmanova and many other artists became popular using modern pop styles in their songs. This genre made Uzbek pop music more popular among young people.

Hip-hop and rap genres also had a great influence on Uzbek music. Uzbek rap artists, such as Radius-21, Shokhrukh and Shakhriyor, have successfully integrated this genre into national music. The rhythmic and powerful forms of expression of this genre aroused great interest among the young generation and allowed to express social issues in songs.

With the development of electronic music, this genre is also widely used in Uzbek pop music. Artists such as DJ Pilgrim, DJ Nariman added electronic elements to their creations and created new musical compositions. These musics became more popular in dance parties and club culture. Although rock music is traditionally less common in Uzbekistan, this genre has also had an impact. Artists such as Yalla (folk rock), Original, Bolalar (disco, pop rock) and Sahar bands have attracted new listeners by using rock elements in their music. Rock music is characterized by its strong voice and guitar tones and breathed new life into national pop music. R&B and Soul genres also brought romantic and emotional tones to Uzbek pop music. Songs in these genres express more feelings of love and soul. As examples of artists who have successfully adopted this genre, we can cite several other artists such as Sevara Nazarkhan.

As a result of the influence of foreign modern music genres, fusion styles and experimental musical projects appeared in Uzbek pop music. Artists are creating new and original musical compositions combining different genres. This enriches the national music and adapts it to the modern and global arena. The influence of foreign modern music genres on the Uzbek national variety is large and multifaceted, and it is significantly visible in musical genres, styles, technologies and cultural traditions. Genres such as pop, hip-hop, electronica, rock, R&B and fusion bring new tones and styles to Uzbek music, enriching and developing it.

These influences contribute to the modernization of national music and its recognition in the international arena.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, we can say that. Foreign modern music had a great influence on Uzbek national pop music, which brought Uzbek music to a new level. This influence was manifested in the genres and styles of music, production techniques, performance style and stage culture, international collaborations and lyrical themes. Modern Uzbek pop music is becoming richer as a result of a successful combination of national and international influences. Foreign music had a great influence on Uzbek pop music, enriching and developing it. This influence increased the diversity of Uzbek music and introduced new directions to it.

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